

Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on upland rice

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We studied the response of upland rice TKM9 to *Azospirillum* inoculation.

A large number of efficient *Azospirillum* cultures were isolated from the root tissues of upland rice varieties.

Azospirillum lipoferum was the predominant species. Two isolates, C. 13 and IPI, have been recognized as the most efficient, with N₂-fixing abilities above 26 mg/g of energy source and acetylene-reducing activities (ARA) of the order of 350–400 nmol ethylene/ mg protein per h. The isolates were prepared as peat-based inoculants carrying about 10⁸ cells/g.

The crop was raised under upland conditions with graded levels of N and 40 kg P and K applied basally. Seed and

soil inoculation of *Azospirillum* were used (1 packet inoculum/20 kg seed and 8 packets/ ha).

Azospirillum inoculation significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). Response at 50 and 75 kg N was high. There was also a significant increase in the root surface area. Although both isolates performed well, C.13 was better. Grain yield with 75 kg N and *Azospirillum* inoculation was higher than with 100 kg fertilizer N. □

Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on grain and straw yields of TKM9. Coimbatore, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)		
	Uninoculated control	Inoculated with isolate C.13	Inoculated with isolate IPI	Uninoculated control	Inoculated with isolate C.13	Inoculated with isolate IPI
0	2.2	2.5	2.4	3.5	3.8	3.6
50	2.6	2.7	2.8	3.7	4.6	4.4
75	2.9	3.5	3.4	4.2	4.7	4.7
103	3.3	3.3	3.3	4.8	4.9	4.9
Mean	2.8	3.0	2.9	4.1	4.5	4.3
		CD (P = 0.01)			CD (P = 0.01)	
Treatment		0.5			0.1	
N		0.6			0.2	
Interaction		1.1			0.3	

Effect of leaf leachates of neem and sirish on the biomass production and pests of *Azolla pinnata*

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Azolla is an attractive host for a wide variety of pests, particularly snails (*Limnaea acuminata*), moths (*Nymphula*, *Pyralis*), and fungus (*Rhizoctonia solani*). We studied the effect of leaf leachates of several plants. Concrete pots with 1,964 cm² surface area were filled with 2 kg oven-dry soil plus 15 liters tap water. Fresh leaves (200 g) of *Albizia lebback* (sirish) or *Azadirachta indica* (neem) were suspended in pots inoculated with 20 g fresh green *azolla* plants, in 3 replications. The pots were placed in an open area with full sunlight for 6 wk during Apr–May at 40.5–42.0 temperature, and light intensity 105–115 klx. Half the biomass was harvested weekly. Insect, fungus, and snail

Influence of leachate of neem and sirish leaves on *azolla* biomass production. West Bengal, India.

Medium	Green biomass production (g/pot)					
	1st wk	2d wk	3d wk	4th wk	5th wk	6th wk
Leaf leachate of neem	56.5	84.0	168.2	246.3	259.0	242.2
Leaf leachate of sirish	59.0	78.0	152.3	85.2	25.5	–
Control	52.5	62.5	78.1	29.4	–	–
LSD (P=0.05)				7.0		

incidence was recorded during each harvest.

Plants cultured in sirish and neem leaf leachates were emerald green, with good growth and with no insects or snails up to the third week (see table). Control plants turned brown after 6 d, with poor growth leading to complete degeneration after 28 d. Seven insects and nine snails

were observed. With leachate of sirish leaves, 5 insects and 29 snails were found, leading to disappearance of the mass after 32 d, although the plant was still green. With leachate of neem leaves, only three snails and no insects were found and plants were green throughout the experiment. In no case were fungal symptoms observed. □

Efficiency of *azolla* as an organic N source for rice

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We laid out a 3-yr experiment at the Cropping Systems Research Centre during 1983–86 wet and dry seasons. Treatments were *azolla* alone, *azolla* in combination with nitrogenous fertilizers and N fertilizers alone, at

three N levels in a randomized block design with four replications. P and K (17.5 kg P, 33 kg K/ha) were constant for all treatments, including control.

Chemical analysis established 4% N content of azolla, based on dry weight. Azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha at transplanting, with 3.5 kg P/ha, recorded a fresh weight of 5 t/ha at incorporation 20 d after transplanting.

In the wet season, yields with N fertilizer were consistently higher than that of control (see table).

Yield with fresh azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha with 3.5 kg P/ha and incorporated 20 d after inoculation were equal to yields with 5 t fresh azolla/ha incorporated before planting.

In the dry season, yields with 90 kg N/ha were significantly higher than in all other treatments. Azolla at 5 t/ha yielded 0.6 t/ha more than control.

The actual benefit of azolla in combination with fertilizer was rather inconsistent. But azolla alone showed significantly higher yields than control. This study suggests alternative fertilizer strategies when chemical fertilizers are scarce or expensive. □

Effect of azolla alone and in combination with N fertilizers on rice yield.^a Orissa, India, 1983.

Treatment per hectare	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Difference
<i>Wet season</i>		
90 kg N	3.7	1.8
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla	3.2	1.3
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.2
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.6	0.7
5 t azolla inoculated and incorporated at 20 DT ^b	2.6	0.7
Control	1.9	—
CD (0.05)	0.2	—
CV (%)	6	—
<i>Dry season</i>		
90 kg N	3.8	2.0
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
10 t azolla + 60 kg N	3.4	1.6
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.3
10 t azolla	3.1	1.3
30 kg N	3.0	1.1
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.8	0.9
5 t azolla	2.4	0.6
Control	1.8	—
CD (0.05)	0.1	—
CV (%)	4	—

^aMeans of 3 yr, 1983-86. ^bDays after transplanting.

Effect of gypsum and pyrite with different moisture regimes on sodic soil improvement and rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of adding 7.25 meq gypsum/100 g soil (50% G.R.) and pyrite equivalent to gypsum on sulfur basis at 3 moisture regimes (continuous saturation [CS], continuous flooding [CF], and alternate saturation and flooding [ASF]) on the improvement of sodic soil and on yield in a pot with 3 replications. Soil was highly sodic, with pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 95, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.45 meq/100 g soil, organic C 0.22%, CaCO₃, 2.75%, CEC 10.0

meq/100 g soil, and gypsum requirement 14.5 meq/100 g soil.

Gypsum and pyrite were added to soil in 10-kg glazed clay pots 2 wk before transplanting 30-d-old Pusa 2-21 seedlings. The moisture regimes were maintained from transplanting to crop maturity. Urea at 80 ppm N and zinc sulfate at 4.5 ppm Zn were applied — half the N and all the Zn at transplanting, the remaining N topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

Gypsum was better than pyrite in improving soil and yield of rice at all three moisture regimes. While CF proved more effective when gypsum was applied, ASF did better with pyrite (Table 1, 2). Growing of rice under CF facilitated greater sodic soil improvement. □

Table 1. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on soil pH and ESP after rice harvest. Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	pH (1:2) soil water			ESP		
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite
Continuous saturation	10.40	9.20	9.70	81.5	41.2	51.8
Alternate saturation – flooding	10.35	9.00	9.40	78.4	36.1	48.5
Continuous flooding	10.35	8.80	9.90	79.7	25.4	65.2

Table 2. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on rice grain yield.^a Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	Grain yield (g/pot)			
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Mean
Continuous saturation	1.10	12.67	5.77	6.51
Alternate saturation – flooding	1.47	14.87	8.40	8.24
Continuous flooding	1.93	18.40	4.13	8.15
Mean	1.50	15.31	6.10	

^aCD at P = 0.05: amendments = 0.72, moisture regimes = 0.72, amendments × moisture regimes = 1.25.

Availability to wetland rice of nitrogen from cattle manure

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Mineralization and availability of N from organic manure will be affected by its C-to-N ratio, soil management, and climatic conditions. Since only a part of organic N will be mineralized during the

growing season of rice, a residual effect of manures is expected in the following crop. We compared the availability of N from cattle manure with urea N to wetland rice. Residual effect was evaluated in a following wheat crop.

Soil of the experimental field was a Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.6, 0.34% organic C, 0.05% total N, and a water percolation rate of 4.5 mm/h. Treatments were 4 rates of N (0, 60, 120,